

Increasing rice production by using terpenoids

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The introduction of semidwarf tropical indica plant type varieties has substantially improved rice production. We are attempting to raise the yields above the present 10 t/ha potential by using terpenoids and their synthetic derivatives as plant growth regulators.

PR106 seeds were treated with solutions of known and recently synthesized terpenoids/essential oils.

Effect of growth regulators on rice yield, Ludhiana, India.

Treatment		1981 kharif		1983 kharif	
		Yield (t/ha)	Percent of control	Yield (t/ha)	Percent of control
Essential oil from <i>Cyperus scariosus</i>	100 ppm	9.9	106	6.0	111
	200 ppm	—	—	5.4	102
Zerumbone	100 ppm	10.5	112	5.5	103
	200 ppm	—	—	5.8	108
C ₁₆ -Guaianolide	100 ppm	10.0	107	5.7	107
	200 ppm	—	—	5.7	106
Control		9.3	100	5.3	100

Solutions were prepared by dissolving the desired quantity of the compounds in small quantity of alcohol and then adding warm water to the desired volume. Seeds were soaked in this

solution for 24 h. Five-wk-old seedlings from treated and untreated (control) seeds were planted at 20 × 15-cm spacing in 1981 and 1983 kharif, and yield was recorded (see table). □

Efficiency of P fertilizers as determined by IR20 grain yield

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We conducted a pot experiment to determine the relative efficiency of P fertilizers as determined by rice grain yield. Soil was alluvial with low Olsen's P (8 kg/ha), 950 ppm P-fixing capacity, pH 6.3, and CEC 54 meq/100 g. The experiment was in a complete randomized design with two replications. Coated and uncoated water-soluble P fertilizers diammonium phosphate (DAP), monoammonium phosphate (MAP), single superphosphate (SSP), and insoluble rock phosphate were applied. P was applied at 26.19, 39.29, and 52.39 kg/ha with 120 kg adjusted total N/ha.

Relative efficiency of different P fertilizers as determined by rice grain yield, Aduthurai, India.

P fertilizer (total P content %)	Grain yield (g/pot)			
	26.19 kg P/ha	39.29 kg P/ha	52.39 kg P/ha	Mean
DAP (20.9)	22.3	24.4	24.8	23.8
MAP (23.6)	17.9	18.4	18.7	18.3
SSP (8.9)	20.6	22.2	22.6	21.8
Coated DAP (10.7)	22.6	23.8	24.6	23.7
Coated MAP (12.1)	17.9	18.7	19.4	18.6
Coated SSP (5.2)	21.3	22.0	22.2	21.8
Rock phosphate (14.8)	15.6	16.8	17.2	16.5
Coated rock phosphate (6.1)	15.7	16.2	16.3	16.1
Mean	19.23	20.31	20.74	20.09
			CD 5%	
			Sources of P	0.54
			Levels of P	0.20
			Interaction	ns

Water-soluble P sources increased rice grain yield more efficiently than insoluble P (see table). DAP gave the maximum yield followed by SSP and MAP. Coated

and uncoated treatments produced similarly. Increased P application enhanced grain production. Interaction effects were insignificant. □

Varietal tolerance for bentazon in direct-seeded lowland rice

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Controlling rice weeds with selective post-emergence herbicides is gaining importance in direct-seeded lowland rice. We evaluated the effect of postemergence herbicide application on weed growth and grain yield of direct-seeded lowland IR36, Mahsuri, and T141 in wet season. The

Effect of bentazon on grain yield of 3 rice cultivars and weed mortality, Orissa, India.

Treatment	IR36			Mahsuri			T141		
	Weeds ^a (no./m ²)	Weed wt ^b (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Weeds ^a (no./m ²)	Weed wt ^b (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Weeds ^a (no./m ²)	Weed wt ^b (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Bentazon @ 2 kg/ha	97	108	2.6	75	66	3.0	66	49	2.0
Bentazon @ 2 kg/ha + 2,4-D @ 1 kg/ha	58	48	2.9	52	39	3.3	40	27	2.4
Two hand weedings at 25 and 45 d after seeding	37	21	3.2	32	20	3.4	29	18	2.2
Untreated and unweeded control	412	217	1.1	277	169	1.6	219	104	1.8

^a60 d after sowing, ^b90 d after sowing.